

1 **JC encephalitis as a common outcome of immunosuppression demonstrates latent JC infection in**
2 **man.**

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7 Immunosuppression from HIV-1 infection, from solid organ transplant and from use of monoclonal
8 antibodies targeting integrins in humans with multiple sclerosis results in PML, a disease caused by
9 activation of latent JC virus in the brain. The data conclusively demonstrate latent JC virus infection in
10 man. We establish here a cell culture model of JC virus using primary choroid plexus epithelial cells and
11 microarray sequencing of total transcription in the host cell.

12 Citations

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GSE264236

GSE45639